

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: MURINDAHABI****FIRST NAME: EPIPHANIE****PROGRAM CODE: DIPH****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA****Edit or delete text to show the actual information below:**

The author applied US UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics (only keep US or UK)

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did did not use Zotero to insert references (remove unneeded text to indicate)

The author did did not use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID) (remove unneeded text)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: xx%

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 8)

List 5 to 7 key concepts with page numbers in text (then bold these terms in your RP) (samples below):

1. Introduction
2. Essay writing (EUCLID 2021, 7-8)
3. Researching the Topic (EUCLID 2021, 8-9)
4. Essay paragraphs (EUCLID 2021, 11)
5. Referencing the Essay (EUCLID 2021, 11)
6. Punctuation (EUCLID 2021, 15-23)
7. Conclusion

WRITE THE TITLE GIVEN TO RP

1) INTRODUCTION

I have always helped my children compose and perfect academic essays when applying to the university for undergraduate programs. I am glad to start the Doctorate in International Public Health (DIPH) Program with the course of International Academic Methods (ACA-401D). The course will also help me perform academic reports, and it is an important part of my studies, from the assignments to the final thesis. This is a great opportunity to learn the process of writing at the beginning of the program to get familiar with the requirements needed in essay writing at EUCLID University and how to develop ideas during the discussion.

While reading this coursepack, different concepts kept my attention not only because they are new concepts for me but also because some of them were little grammatical mistakes that did not take my attention many times ago. Learning them will improve my writing level and help me perform the academic reports well. The five concepts that capture my attention include essay writing, researching the topic, essay paragraphs, referencing the essay, and punctuation.

2) ESSAY WRITING

The first chapter of the course park relates to essay writing, intending to show the basics of essay writing, the steps for writing a good essay, and some rules of thumb for writing a paper (EUCLID 2021, 7).

I retained that the essay is a story or a report that informs the reader about a well-organized event or evidence, well generated consequently, supporting theories, or challenging them by providing some reasons that need to be considered for an eventual change. It starts with an idea, formulated into a question that guides the whole essay writing.

The author advises to start the essay early to have enough time to read and conduct research on a given subject. He recommends having a work plan to follow and how to approach the work, and he has put in place the important steps to take to have a complete work to present and share.

The writing process involves approximately four stages. In the first step, you take time to read and research the topic, think, and write different ideas. In the second step, you define the question and analyze the task guiding the work. In the third step, you write a draft that includes your initial thoughts and ideas, and that will guide your research. In the final step, you refine your draft by editing it and making revisions by having a second reader to help you (EUCLID 2021, 8).

Writing takes time and requires special attention. It is better to write about something you know and that you will be proud to present and share the result. It requires time to be able to correct errors, review ideas, and adjust them well. I realized that it is a long process, but when we reach the end, we are proud of the work.

3) RESEARCHING THE TOPIC

It has not been easy to find a research topic. But when it is fixed, you are requested to conduct reading related to the subjects. Reading and researching will provide the opportunity to get updated information related to the topic and an orientation on how to respond to the question posed at the beginning.

The author suggested important questions we need to know before starting the reading. He emphasizes that you need to know about the subject that you are searching for. This will guide you on where to orient the research readings, what to read, and what to retain. The choice of reading materials is also important, as it is an academic requirement.

Researching is an important part of writing as it helps to choose relevant information.

4) ESSAY PARAGRAPHS

An essay paragraph is an important part of writing since it is the one that helps express a given idea. I did not realize how smart it is to build and develop a paragraph by starting with the introduction, the body, and the conclusion. When I was reading this part, I found out how writing requires more attention in organizing ideas. That is also what I am doing now since I reviewed almost everything I have written to adjust my ideas.

As more than two ideas cannot be developed into one paragraph, it is important to plan and highlight what to discuss to be able to give more information related to one topic. This helps to organize ideas and use theories that support what we express.

5) REFERENCING THE ESSAY

When writing an essay, we cannot use only our ideas but also other authors' thoughts, theories, and experiences. That is why referencing is used to tell the reader where ideas come from. Referring to the source is like giving support to your idea, and the reader will pay more attention to your prompt if he finds out that others have the same idea, which would make the proposition more credible.

Referencing is also an important part of writing since it acknowledges the source of information. Different types of referencing exist, and I am glad Euclid University acknowledges all forms of referencing if they are strict in their formats (EUCLID, 2021, 11). Failure to properly acknowledge sources is called plagiarism, which is prohibited in academic work.

6) PUNCTUATION

Punctuation has been taught since elementary school, but I did not realize how important and difficult it still is in writing an essay. The guidelines found in this course park on this point opened my eyes even to the use of the full stop when listing items or writing a title. This shows how important this course is since we can ignore certain elements learned a long time ago or something that we did not have time to master because we come from different fields that do not value this type of thing. It is an element of grammar that has not been valued but is very important in the world of writing.

7) CONCLUSION

The five concepts above are those that caught my attention in the period one coursepack. The goal of an academic essay is to provide an answer to a question posed. There is a process to follow, even if it is not linear only the point of view indicates the path to follow. It is advisable to just start early so that you have time to do research and read on

relevant topics. The reading will enrich your ideas, and it is necessary to articulate each idea in a paragraph.

Paragraph writing is essential because when it is well developed, it makes a good essay, and the reader enjoys reading and gradually discovers or finds answers. Reference has a good impact on the writing of an essay since it gives value to the ideas of others and credibility to the person presenting them. It is useful to start this program with this course to recall the terms for writing a good essay, a work which will close this program, and be useful to us in the daily work when we are asked to elaborate a report, a concept notes, or abstract; we will always remember these guidelines.

REFERENCES

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